

**НЕДОПУСТИМОСТЬ ПРИЗНАНИЯ ЯВКИ С ПОВИННОЙ И
«ЧИСТОСЕРДЕЧНОГО ПРИЗНАНИЯ», ПОЛУЧЕННЫХ БЕЗ УЧАСТИЯ
ЗАЩИТНИКА, ОСНОВНЫМИ ДОКАЗАТЕЛЬСТВАМИ ПО
УГОЛОВНОМУ ДЕЛУ**

**INADMISSIBILITY OF CONFESSIONS AND «SINCERE CONFESSIONS»
OBTAINED WITHOUT THE PARTICIPATION OF COUNSEL, MAIN
EVIDENCE IN A CRIMINAL CASE**

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Данная работа посвящена одной из существующих проблем в современном уголовно-процессуальном законодательстве, а именно признанию явки с повинной, полученной следственными органами от гражданина без участия защитника (адвоката), и использованию такой «явки с повинной» в качестве доказательства по уголовному делу. Подчеркивается, что данная проблема влечет за собой существенное нарушение конституционных прав граждан в уголовном процессе и, соответственно, незаконное привлечение их к уголовной ответственности. Сделан вывод, что явка с повинной является наиболее удобным способом закрепления признательных показаний, в отличие от иных форм доказательств, поскольку она практически не регламентирована на нормативном уровне и допускает признание вины до возбуждения уголовного дела.

This work is devoted to one of the existing problems in modern criminal procedure legislation, namely, the recognition of a confession obtained by the investigative authorities from a citizen without the participation of a defender (lawyer), and the use of such a "confession" as evidence in a criminal case. It is emphasized that this problem entails a significant violation of the constitutional rights of citizens in criminal proceedings and, accordingly, illegal bringing them to criminal responsibility. It is concluded that a confession is the most convenient way to consolidate confessions, unlike other forms of evidence, since it is practically not regulated at the regulatory level and allows admission of guilt before the initiation of a criminal case.

Ключевые слова: явка с повинной, права, преступление, защитник, обвинение, государство, защитник.

Key words: *confession, rights, crime, defender, prosecution, state, defender.*

Research relevance. The relevance of this topic can be seen in the large number of cases in the jurisprudence indicating that the accused (defendant) did not have a sign of voluntariness when writing the protocol of surrender.

Over the past decade, the number of illegal convicts in Russia has exceeded tens of thousands of persons, affecting the State's economic, social and legal development.

Unfortunately, the current provisions of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation do not provide for the right of a person surrendering, to receive qualified legal assistance from a lawyer who would record by his presence the fact of voluntary confession of a citizen in the commission of a crime and would accordingly exclude the fact of a statement about the commission of a crime, which can be written under psychological pressure of operatives, or using other unlawful methods of investigation. In addition, article 15 of the Code of Criminal Procedure establishes the constitutional principle of the adversarial nature of criminal proceedings. According to paragraph 4 of the said article, the parties to the prosecution and the defence are equal before the court. However, as practice shows, the principle of the adversarial nature of the parties in criminal proceedings is only declaratory and cannot be implemented during the preliminary and judicial investigation of a criminal case [5, c.90].

The statement of the law in subsequent articles of the Code of Criminal Procedure shows that there is no such equality between the parties and, consequently, that the principle of adversarial proceedings is not respected in practice.

Article 49, paragraph 3, of the Code of Criminal Procedure contains an exhaustive list of points from which defence counsel is entitled to participate in criminal proceedings.

In accordance with the provisions of paragraph 6.1 of article 53 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, defence counsel has the right, from the moment of entering into a criminal case, to consult the record of detention and the decision on the application of the measure Preventive measures, reports of investigative actions carried out with the participation of the suspect or the accused, other documents which were or should have been presented to the suspect or accused. Thus, we see gaps in the right to a citizen's right to a defence, firstly, the person who confesses without the obligatory participation of the defender, secondly, the defender is deprived of the right to consult the text of the confession, which therefore puts him in an inherently unequal position with the prosecution [2, c.33]. The contradictions described above between the norms of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation and the Constitution of the Russian Federation and the norms of the Russian Federation's criminal procedural legislation require the immediate amendment of certain articles of the Criminal CodeThe Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation for the purpose of respecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, which will ultimately contribute to the establishment of a State governed by the rule of law in the Russian Federation.

The concept of surrendering and distinguishing it from an honest confession

Article 142 of the Criminal Procedure Law of the Russian Federation sets out the concept of surrender:

1. Declaration of surrender - voluntary reporting of a person about the crime committed by him.

2. A written or oral application may be made. The oral statement shall be accepted and recorded in the order established by the third part of Article 141 of this Code.» Consider the more common meaning of this concept.»

Surrendering is the voluntary personal treatment (appearance) of a person who has committed a crime, with a statement that a crime has been committed to the body of inquiry, investigator, prosecutor or court and with the desire to hand over himself to justice before being charged or

suspected. In this way we can see that the obligatory sign of surrender should be considered - voluntariness. In order to reach a conclusion about the voluntary nature of the actions of the perpetrator when surrendering, it is necessary to establish his free will to do so and that he has the possibility to choose other options for his conduct, rather than reporting the crime under duress of evidence.

Only a citizen's statement which relates to a crime not known to the law enforcement authorities at all, in other words, unreported, or a crime known but not solved, when a person The perpetrator was not established by investigation and there was no suspect or accused in the case file, and the statement of surrender was made solely on a voluntary basis [1, c. 113]. As a rule, however, based on investigative practice, a person turns himself in after arrest, when the law enforcement agencies have information about a citizen's involvement in the crime, which became known from the evidence or other evidence.

Let us consider the point, which is important in the study of this work, namely, how is it worth distinguishing a confession and a confession? Confession (repentance) is a colloquial expression implying that the guilty party must voluntarily disclose during the inquiry, preliminary or judicial investigation all the circumstances of the crime committed, containing a negative assessment of the actions of the perpetrator and those of his accomplices. One of the effective means of helping to solve criminal offences is surrender. An individual who has confessed to an investigation can not only give truthful testimony about his or her criminal activities, but also about crimes committed by others. They can be assisted in locating items and in finding exhibits. Reporting (in accordance with Art. 61 of the Criminal Code) may be accompanied by an honest confession of guilt and condemnation of one's conduct.

In the event that the perpetrator was apprehended, with the assistance of the victims or the testimony of witnesses, his confession would not be considered a confession. But as court practice has shown, the court may consider such an action as a mitigating circumstance.

Nature of surrender and regulatory regulation

Article 51 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation states that a citizen must not testify against himself, article 48 establishes the right to defend himself, that is, to use the services of a lawyer, It should also explain the possibility of complaining about acts or omissions of public authorities.

Surrendering does not explicitly require the presence of a lawyer, but article 48 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation expressly provides for the right to defence of a lawyer, without dividing at which stages of the investigation it must be exercised. According to the provisions of the Constitution cited above, a confession may be accepted as proof if the person has been given all possible guarantees and explained all rights, but the possibility of exercising these rights must be effectively ensured, This means that a lawyer must be present for the purposes of the right of defence. It can be concluded that the use of confessions obtained in the absence of legal aid diminishes the fairness of criminal proceedings in general.

The Act does not prescribe to warn a person who has surrendered of criminal liability for knowingly false denunciation. In our view, such a proposal is not entirely correct, as the requirement to warn of criminal liability for knowingly false denunciation of a person reporting a crime is contrary to Article. 51 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, according to which no one is obliged to testify against himself.

In addition, research shows that, quite often, a confession is the result of physical and psychological pressure on the person by the operative officers in the event of direct detection of signs of crime prior to the registration of the crime (approximately 73 per cent of all surrenders). Thus, even this fact alone suffices for a lawyer to be present.

An important aspect is that the courts, referring to the surrender as «full» evidence, ignore the fact that it actually occurs in the context of a fundamental violation of the right to defence.

In conclusion, in our view, the current version of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation violates the principle of equality of the parties and their adversarial nature in criminal proceedings, since there is no lawyer present at the time of surrender, This violates the right to a defence.

It should also be noted that, at present, reporting is considered not only as a mitigating circumstance but also as evidence in a criminal case. However, the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation does not determine to which type of evidence this record should be attributed. Art. 74 The Code of Criminal Procedure contains an exhaustive list of evidence, among which there is no confession. Surrendering (and drawing up an appropriate protocol) is neither an investigative nor a procedural act, therefore the protocol of surrender cannot be considered as evidence [4, c.55].

Thus, the legal nature of the surrender raises many theoretical and practical questions that need to be resolved in order to prevent abuse of rights in criminal proceedings.

Objective and solution to the problem

The aim of our work is to establish the basic principle of the criminal procedure - the presumption of innocence, as well as the legality and voluntariness of the actions of those who have declared themselves guilty.

Furthermore, we consider it inadmissible to exert physical and emotional pressure on these persons in order to solve the crime as soon as possible.

In order to realize our goal, it is necessary to identify solutions to this problem, which should be further described in the amendment of the Russian Federation's criminal procedure legislation.

In connection with the study, two objectives should be set:

1. Surrendering should not be considered as basic evidence in a case if the evidence was obtained without the participation of counsel. The participation of the defence counsel will significantly reduce the number of cases of unlawful influence on such a person. It will be possible to react quickly to illegal actions of law enforcement officials:

Conduct of an examination;

Reporting a crime against a person who has surrendered, etc.

2. Amend article 142 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation (Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation) by adding paragraph 3 and redraft it as follows:

3. A statement of surrender may be made only in the presence of counsel. If a statement of surrender is made in the absence of a lawyer, the statement of surrender must be considered insufficient evidence for a conviction»

Features of registration and proposed changes to the application for surrender

There are two ways in which a person may turn himself in, orally or by written application:

In the first case, information about the crime committed is accepted and recorded in the record, which is regulated in paragraph 2 of article 142 of the Code of Criminal Procedure.

In the second case, information about the perpetrators must be recorded in a strictly regulated form, which is regulated in article 141, paragraph 3, of the Code of Criminal Procedure.

In the second case, it should take the form of a standard statement, the text of which is in free form. If an application is written to the internal affairs agencies, the applicant will necessarily be given a special form. It is filled in according to these requirements, and the empty blocks are the key information in the case.

When making an appearance, it is necessary to specify in the application:

The name of the office and name of the chief in whose name the document will be sent;

- information about the applicant;

- in the following main part, it is reasonable to state that the applicant is fully aware of the essence of 51 articles of the Constitution of the Russian Federation (absence of the obligation to

testify against oneself, one's relatives, etc. - this is necessary to emphasize that the appearance is voluntary (and there were no unnecessary questions, difficulties, and so on. n.)

- then it is necessary to start the narrative with the words: «In accordance with article 142 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation I wish to inform...» after which, in a free, but clear and adequate form, full information about the committed offence is given;

- it is also important to specify the general description of the crime: location, time (at least approximate), list of witnesses/eyewitnesses, and key circumstances of the incident.

At the end of the document is the date of writing, a little lower - name of the applicant, and on the contrary – a signature.

For the legality of the writing of the confession, we propose to slightly change the format of writing and include in the application line: «The statement is written in the personal and official presence of the lawyer (defender)», add the initials, date and signature of the defender.

Conclusions

From the conducted study, analyzing the essence of the problem, the ways of solution can be said about the fact That the proposed amendments to the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation with regard to surrendering will fully guarantee the protection of citizens' rights in criminal proceedings established and other normative acts.

Due to the fact that surrendering is not an urgent procedural act and is not limited to procedural time, the law enforcement authorities will have every opportunity to provide the person with a lawyer, so the proposed change will not bring any or procedural problems or difficulties in securing legal counsel.

The compulsory participation of a lawyer will allow the accused to have a private, confidential conversation with him, at which he can learn from him about the voluntariness of turning himself in or away, and he will also attest to the observance of all constitutional human rights.

If this rule is changed, surrender will no longer be considered the only evidence in court, the judges will examine the case more thoroughly, and require only credible evidence.

Since there is a new procedural situation in which the legitimization of confessions is possible only with the participation of lawyers, this must be taken into account in the Standard for the Participation of Defence Counsel in Criminal Proceedings being drafted.

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